

Magneto-optical Rotation of Uranyl Salts.

BY S. S. BHATNAGAR, P. L. KAPUR AND N. R. VERMA.

Magneto-optical rotation, both by sign and magnitude, can furnish considerable information with regard to the structure of substances and can supplement the conclusions arrived at by other physico-chemical methods. The usefulness of this method with respect to structural problems has been fully established by Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1884, 45, 421 ; 1885, 47, 240; *cf.* also Bhatnagar and Mathur, "Physical Principles and Applications of Magneto-Chemistry," Macmillan & Co., London, 1935) and others in the case of organic compounds but its application to inorganic compounds has not been fully explored. The authors' purpose is to undertake a systematic study of ions in different valency states and in the present paper they have studied some of the uranyl salts. The salts of uranium are of a particular interest, because in the case of this element, like that of iron, palladium and platinum, the incomplete shell is the inner *d*-shell with a room for 10 more electrons according to the Pauli exclusion principle. Whereas in the case of iron salts, there is a general agreement between the theoretical and experimental magnetic moments (Bhatnagar and Mathur, *loc. cit.*). This does not seem to be the case with the compounds of uranium. This deviation has been attributed to the complex formation in the aqueous solution, particularly in the case of uranium ions of lower valency state. Lawrence (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 776), has for example, shown that with varying hydrogen ion concentration of the solution, the magnetic susceptibility varies considerably. We have for this reason selected for the present only the uranyl salts for investigation, for in addition to being in the maximum valency state, the uranyl ion exhibits paramagnetism independent of temperature. This type of anomalous paramagnetism is associated with zero Bohr magneton number in such atomic group formations.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Three uranyl salts namely uranyl nitrate, chloride and sulphate were obtained and purified in the laboratory by repeated crystallisations from water. The three salts were further analysed for uranium

and acid radical content. The absence of paramagnetic impurities like manganese, molybdenum and iron, as well as of the uranium salts in lower valency state, was made sure of by standard methods (Noyes and Brans, "Qualitative Analysis for the Rare Elements", Macmillan and Co., New York, 1927; Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", John Wiley and Sons). As a further check the magnetic susceptibilities of the sulphate and nitrate were determined by a Curie-Wilson balance and compared against the standard values given in literature.

The magneto-optical rotations of these salts were determined by the method employed by Bhatnagar and Kapur (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 767) and the values of molecular rotations (M) were calculated by the formula,

$$M = \frac{D_2}{D_1} \left[\frac{\mu W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + W_s}{\rho \cdot W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \right] - \mu \times m$$

where D_2 denotes the rotation of the solution; D_1 , the rotation of water; μ , the ratio of the number of molecules of water to one molecule of the solute; ρ , the density of solution; $W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, the molecular weight of water; W_s is the molecular weight of solute; m , the molecular rotation of water taken as unity.

After each determination the quantity of the particular salt in the solution was found by analysing a known volume of the solution for the uranium content by the oxide method (Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis," D. Von Nostrand and Co., Vol. I) and the quantity of the anhydrous salt was calculated from this. The density of each of the solution was also determined by a 10 c.c. specific gravity bottle. The results obtained are shown in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Uranyl nitrate.

$$W = 394.17, \quad W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 18.$$

No.	Vol.	Density.	W e i g h t o f		Mols of solvent		D_2/D_1 .	M .
			soln.	solvent.	solvent.	Mols of solute		
5c	45 c.c.	1.114	50.12g.	43.8839g.	6.2361	154.1	7.82/8.33	-5.70
5d	45	1.075	48.38	44.2226	4.1574	232.8	7.97/8.33	-6.0
5e	45	1.052	47.35	44.5784	2.7716	352.1	8.13/8.33	-5.96
6a	50	1.237	61.85	47.8250	14.0250	74.66	7.29/8.28	-5.35
6b	45	1.157	52.06	43.6450	8.415	113.6	7.60/8.28	-6.1

TABLE II.

Uranyl chloride.

$$W_s = 341.09. W_{H_2O} = 18.$$

No.	Vol.	Density.	Weight of soln.	Weight of solvent.	Weight of solute.	$\frac{\text{Mols of solvent}}{\text{Mols of solute}}$	D_2/D_1 .	M.
2a	50	1.175	58.75g.	48.575g.	10.175g.	90.4	8.37/8.55	0.65
2b	45	1.116	50.22	44.115	6.105	137.0	8.47/8.55	1.50
3b	45	1.094	49.23	43.990	5.2335	159.3	8.45/8.55	1.50

TABLE III.

Uranyl sulphate.

$$W_s = 366.17. W_{H_2O} = 18$$

No.	Vol.	Density.	Weight of soln.	Weight of solvent.	Weight of solute.	$\frac{\text{Mols of solvent}}{\text{Mols of solute}}$	D_2/D_1 .	M.
1a	50 c. c.	1.151	57.55 g.	49.505 g.	8.045 g.	125.1	7.935/8.56	-8.0
1b	45	1.102	49.59	44.763	4.827	138.7	8.112/8.56	-9.0
1d	60	1.026	61.56	59.951	1.609	758.0	8.46/8.56	-8.4

DISCUSSION.

The molecular rotation value due to the uranyl ion can be calculated by subtracting the rotation due to other ions from that of the pure salt. From Anderson and Asmusen's data (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 2827) on a series of inorganic compounds the following values for rotations of different substances and ions have been obtained: Cl^- , 4.43; $(NH_4)_2SO_4$, 4.99; $(NH_4)^+$, 1.00.

By subtracting the molecular rotation on account of NH_4^+ from that of the sulphate, the rotation of the sulphate radical comes out to be 2.99. Similarly the rotation of the nitrate group as calculated from Humburg's data (*Z. Physik*, 1893, 12, 401) work out to be 1.150.

In Table IV are given the rotation values due to the uranyl ion.

TABLE IV.

Salt.	No.	M .	M_{anion}	$M_{(\text{UO}_2)}$..
Uranyl nitrate	5c	-5.70	$2 \times 1.150 = 2.30$	$-5.7 - 2.3 = -8.0$
	5d	-6.00	..	$-6.0 - 2.3 = -8.3$
	5e	-5.96	..	$-5.95 - 2.3 = -8.25$
	6a	-5.93	..	$-5.93 - 2.3 = -8.23$
	6b	-6.1	..	$-6.1 - 2.3 = -8.4$
Uranyl chloride	2a	0.65	$2 \times 4.43 = 8.86$	$0.65 - 8.86 = -8.21$
	2b	1.50	..	$1.50 - 8.86 = -7.36$
	8b	1.50	..	$1.50 - 8.89 = -7.36$
Uranyl sulphate	1a	-8.0	2.99	$-8.0 - 2.99 = -10.99$
	1b	-9.0	2.99	$-9.0 - 2.99 = -11.99$
	1d	-8.4	2.99	$-8.4 - 2.99 = -11.39$

It may be seen that value for rotation of UO_2 has in each case a negative sign and in the case of individual salts is fairly constant over a wide range of concentration. One more fact which is quite significant is that the molecular rotation value due to uranyl radical has nearly the same value in the case of the nitrate and the chloride but the case of the sulphate shows a much different rotation. This difference in molecular magnetic rotation value of UO_2 in the case of sulphate may be due to the existence of some complex formation. On analysing completely all the three salts the composition of the chloride and the nitrate proved to be UO_2Cl_2 and $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$, but that of the sulphate worked out to be $2\text{UO}_2 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ corresponding to the formula of Wyrobouff (*Bull. Soc. franc., min.*, 1909, 32, 340). Our observation of the Faraday-effect, therefore, show that the anomaly may be due to the sulphuric acid molecule entering into complex formation with the uranyl ion thus affecting the value of molecular rotation.

The magnetic susceptibility of the uranyl ion as a sulphate has been determined in aqueous solutions (Lawrence, *loc. cit.*) as well in the solid state (Freed and Kasper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4671). The ion has been found to be slightly paramagnetic though the susceptibility is independent of temperature.

It is significant to note that certain compounds which exhibit anomalous paramagnetism with respect to temperature also show that Faraday-effect independent of temperature, for example (Mlle) Collet (*Compt. rend.*, 1926 183, 1031) observed that the paramagnetic susceptibility of KMnO_4 and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ does not show any variation with temperature. Also Pillai (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1932, 6, 573) showed that Faraday-effect in these compounds is as well independent of temperature. One may, therefore, expect the rotation of the uranyl salts also not to be affected by temperature since their susceptibility does not show any variation under the conditions. This, however, is not a general rule, for there are substances like manganese chloride and cobalt nitrate which obey Weiss law but show a constant magneto-optical rotation over the range of temperature investigated. Work, however, on the effect of temperature on the magneto-optical rotation of uranyl salts is in progress. We are also studying the effect of addition of free acids of the magneto-optical rotation of these salts.

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The Anomalous Rotatory Dispersion of l - β Pinene. Part I.

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In a previous work (Padmanabhan and Jatkar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 56, 334) on the rotatory dispersion of seven isomeric hydrocarbons of the formula $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$, the interesting observation that the optical rotatory power of d -sabinene passes through a maximum at about λ 3300 Å was made. Since d -sabinene and l - β -pinene are the only substances having anomalous rotatory dispersion known up till now among the optically active hydrocarbons, we felt that further work was desirable in order to throw light upon the origin of the peculiar optical behaviour of these compounds.

The optical rotatory power of l - β -pinene is negative in the visible region of the spectrum, the magnitude changing but slightly with wave-length, becomes zero at about λ 3700 Å and attains high positive values on the shorter wave-length side. This anomalous behaviour was first noticed by Darmsis (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1911, 22, 495) and although both he and quite recently, Servant (*Compt. rend.*,